

Decentring the Study of Migrant
Returns and Return Policies

Political and Human Rights Trade-offs: The Case of Iraq-Sweden and Iraq-Germany Assisted Return Frameworks

(WP9)

Authors:

William K. Warda (Hammurabi Human Rights Organization)

Mohammed T. Al-Obaidi (Hammurabi Human Rights Organization)

D9.1. January 2026

Table of Contents

Executive Summary	1
1. Introduction	3
2. AVRs in Iraq	6
3. Case Studies	7
3.1. The Iraqi-Swedish Readmission Agreement	7
<i>The Gap Between Promise and Practice: Returnee Experiences from Sweden to Iraq</i> ...	8
3.2. The Germany-Iraq Return Framework	11
4. The Trade-offs in the Context of Return Migration in Iraq	13
4.1. Alternative Solutions to Trade-offs in the Context of Return	15
4.1.1. Compensating Human Rights with Equal Assistance for Voluntary Return	15
4.1.2. Political Instability and Abandoned Commitments.....	17
4.1.3. Vulnerability and Differential Harm: Yazidis and Religious Minorities.....	17
5. Discussion and Conclusion	18
6. Recommendations	20
7. References	21

List of abbreviations

CAT	Committee Against Torture
CEDAW	Committee on the Elimination of Discrimination Against Women
CRC	Committee on the Rights of the Child
EU	European Union
ETTC	European Technology and Training Centre
FAO	United Nations Food and Agriculture Organization
FFS	Funding Facility for Stabilization
GIZ	German Corporation for International Cooperation
HHRO	Hammurabi Human Rights Organization
HRC	Human Rights Committee
ICMPD	International Centre for Migration Policy Development
IOM	International Organization for Migration
IQD	Iraqi Dinars
MOU	Memorandum of Understanding
MOFA	Ministry of Foreign Affairs
MOMD	Ministry of Migration and Displacement
NRM	National Referral Mechanism
UN	United Nations
UNDP	United Nations Development Programme
SIDA	Swedish International Development Cooperation Agency
SEK	Swedish Krona

Executive Summary

This report examines how European return policies towards Iraqi migrants generate trade-offs between state interests in migration control and the protection of fundamental human rights within return programmes. It explores return cases from Sweden and Germany, focusing on Assisted Voluntary Return and Reintegration (AVRR) schemes and how these are incorporated within wider political and economic negotiations between the countries of destination (Germany and Sweden) and Iraq. The report provides a concise analysis of bilateral agreements and their practical frameworks, highlighting that “voluntary” return is often perceived as limited. Many Iraqi migrants agree to return not out of true choice but because stricter legal conditions, restricted rights, and lack of alternatives make them feel forced into accepting return offers. In this setting, reintegration support frequently serves as an implicit incentive, often exchanged for a reduction or adjustment of certain rights protections, which raises concerns about the true voluntariness of their consent.

Methodologically, the report integrates the literature on human rights trade-offs within the Iraqi context with a legal analysis of pertinent international and bilateral instruments on asylum and return. It also expands on 250 interviews carried out by HHRO researchers as part of the Horizon Europe GAPS project between August 2024 and April 2025. These interviews involved 153 Iraqi returnees from Germany and Sweden, including those who were forcibly returned and those who took part in AVRR programmes. The data aims to reconstruct their journeys, decision-making processes, and post-return circumstances. These testimonies reveal serious shortcomings in existing programmes: limited access to training, employment, psychosocial support, and basic services; persistent poverty, isolation, and psychological distress; and widespread consideration of re-migration in the absence of sustainable reintegration prospects.

The report identifies critical dimensions of trade-offs:

1. Asymmetric Political Trade-offs

1.1. Return arrangements function as political exchanges: Iraq agrees to deportations in exchange for visa facilitation, development aid, and diplomatic recognition. Although presented as mutually beneficial, these deals hide existing asymmetries—states receive diplomatic influence and relief, while migrants confronted constrained choices between forced deportation and “voluntary” return with minimal support.

1.2. The bilateral agreements (Sweden-Iraq 2008 MOU; Germany-Iraq 2023 Declaration of Intent) were not subject to public consultation or civil society review during drafting and early implementation phases. The reintegration suffers from weak return infrastructure, fragmented institutional responsibilities and opaque and poorly monitored procedures. As such, the development programs and infrastructure mentioned in agreements, are not explicitly connected to benefits or outcomes for returnees

2. Human rights Trade-offs

2.1. “Voluntariness” as Coercive Practice: “Voluntary” return often reflects limited choice rather than true consent. Iraqi returnees agreed to go back not out of free will but because stricter legal conditions, restricted rights, extended limbo, and a lack of alternatives made them feel forced. Financial incentives and support serve as tools that exchange fewer rights for compliance, weakening genuine voluntariness.

2.2. Procedural Trade-Offs and Identity Verification: Bilateral frameworks tend to prioritize efficiency at the expense of due process. The process of verifying identities via biometric exchanges and consular interviews often lacks protections for disputed cases. Speeding up procedures reduces access to legal aid, vulnerability assessments, and remedies, sacrificing procedural integrity in favour of cost savings and political signalling.

2.3. Post-Return Abandonment and Fragmented Reintegration: Returnee testimonies highlight significant shortcomings: scarce employment opportunities, insufficient training, lack of psychosocial support, and limited services; ongoing poverty and hardship; and widespread thoughts of re-migration. Obstacles faced by Iraq include weak infrastructure, fragmented responsibilities, unclear agreements, and limited civil society involvement in policy development and oversight.

The report concludes with recommendations for greater transparency, stronger legal and human-rights oversight, expanded and better-designed post-return support, and closer linkage between any return arrangements and long-term development measures in Iraq.

Cite as

Warda W. and M. T. Al-Obaidi. 2026. Political and Human Rights Trade-offs: The Case of Iraq-Sweden and Iraq-Germany Assisted Return Frameworks. *GAPs Working paper* 2026/02. DOI. 10.5281/zenodo.18160745

1. Introduction¹

The language of trade-offs must be used critically—distinguishing real dilemmas, like resource allocation, from politically constructed choices that reduce binding norms to policy preferences (Huges K., 2025).

Political trade-offs operate as an exchange between countries of origin and destination. This dynamic often manifests in efforts to secure the voluntary return of migrants through formal agreements or diplomatic arrangements that address basic needs meant to support returnees' stability and reintegration. Such arrangements are typically financed or co-funded by the destination country, with both sides pursuing a shared objective: achieving a form of mutual satisfaction that, ideally, also benefits the returning migrants. The drive to increase return rates, cooperate with so-called "safe third countries", and externalize migration controls often creates incentives for restrictive risk assessments, expedited procedures, or forms of "indirect" pressure that ultimately result in people being returned to unsafe conditions. However, these arrangements can entail significant compromises on human rights during the return process itself.

Human-rights trade off start from the onset of asylum procedures to departure, including the post-return period. For example, origin countries may agree to accept returned migrants without strict adherence to the principle of non-refoulement or without adequate safeguards for human dignity, in exchange for development aid targeted at reducing future migration pressures. In this sense, the trade-off includes both positive and negative dimensions—where one is often sacrificed to secure the other. Human rights trade-offs particularly emerge when returns take place without sufficient screening for prior abuse, trafficking experiences, or health-related vulnerabilities, leaving returnees exposed to renewed violence, inadequate medical care, and violations of child rights upon arrival.

In general, human rights trade-offs in return migration emerge where two imperatives collide: the state's drive to control migration and enforce removals, and its duty to uphold the rights, safety, and agency of migrants and refugees. While states seek to operationalize returns as part of credible border and asylum systems, international human rights and refugee law mandate that no one should be sent back to face serious harm and that all procedures must respect dignity, due process, and non-discrimination. These conflicting aims produce trade-offs that are not just legal or technical in nature, but deeply political, distributive, and often gendered, shaping who ultimately bears the risks and costs of what is called "migration management" (Collet & Sommerville, 2014; OHCHR, 2024; Valentine et al., 2024). Such trade-offs become operational when efficiency, deterrence, or the perceived credibility of asylum systems are prioritized over individualized assessments, procedural safeguards, and socio-economic rights during pre- and post-return processes (Collet & Sommerville, 2014; PICUM, 2022).

Human rights standards represent the core values aimed at designed to protect human dignity without discrimination, with particular attention to vulnerable groups such as displaced persons and refugees. Central to these protections is the principle of non-refoulement, set out in Article 33 of the 1951 UN Convention Relating to the Status of Refugees. This principle constitutes a cornerstone of international human rights, refugee, humanitarian, and customary law. Developed through consistent state practice and the absence of objection, it

¹ This research was conducted by the Hammurabi Human Rights Organization within the GAPs project consortium, with collaborative support from HHRO President Pascale Warda. We would like thank the following researchers for their support: Mohammed K. Al-Maeni and Khalid A. Al-Bayati, and GAPs coordinators Zeynep Sahin Mencütek, Soner Barthoma. Translation, editing, and compilation support was provided by Nicholas Al-Jeloo and Mohammed Nour Ahmad.

has gained the status of a binding international norm that prohibits states from expelling or returning individuals when there are substantial grounds to believe they would face irreparable harm—such as persecution, torture, inhuman treatment, or other severe human rights violations.

The protection against refoulement extends well beyond the Refugee Convention itself. It is explicitly reaffirmed in instruments such as the Convention against Torture and Other Cruel, Inhuman or Degrading Treatment or Punishment (CAT) and the International Convention for the Protection of All Persons from Enforced Disappearance (ICPPED). Regional frameworks likewise enshrine this principle, including the Inter-American Convention on the Prevention of Torture, the American Convention on Human Rights, and the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights. International and regional human rights courts, as well as national judiciaries, have consistently recognized non-refoulement as an implicit obligation arising from broader duties to respect, protect, and fulfil human rights. Treaty bodies—such as the Committee Against Torture (CAT), the Human Rights Committee (HRC), the Committee on the Elimination of Discrimination Against Women (CEDAW), and the Committee on the Rights of the Child—routinely address individual petitions concerning alleged violations of this fundamental protection (OHCHR, 2018).

Return as a Political Bargain: The Bilateral Agreements between Iraq and Sweden/ Germany

The historical background of Iraq's bilateral return agreements shows how non-refoulement principles are negotiated within geopolitical contexts. When Iraq's Prime Minister visited Sweden in 2008, Iraqi officials framed return as a sign of restored security and state capacity, facilitating the February 2008 Memorandum of Understanding (MOU) on voluntary return signed by Foreign Minister Hoshiyar Zebari and Swedish Ambassador Niclas Trouvé. The Iraqi Ministry of Foreign Affairs emphasized the importance of voluntary return and the safety of Iraqi citizens, stating that returns would occur in stages with security and care provided. Sweden's investment in the agreement reflected its prioritization of migration control and the belief that the MOU demonstrated confidence in Iraq's democratic future and stability. Similarly, in 2023, Germany and Iraq formalized a "Declaration of Intent" emphasizing legal and labour migration cooperation, with voluntary return as a political quid pro quo: Iraq accepts deportations in exchange for visa facilitation and development assistance. Both agreements assert mutual benefits: host countries reduce irregular migration; Iraq receives development funding and demonstrates state control; migrants receive financial support and return assistance.

However, this perspective conceals a power asymmetry: States gain diplomatic leverage, budget support, and symbolic gains, reputation while individual migrants face limited options in environments without sufficient legal protections and social support. Rather than reflecting genuine confidence in Iraq's ability to readmit its citizens safely, these agreements allowed European states to claim they were returning asylum seekers to a 'safe' country while Iraq leveraged readmission for political and economic concessions. In practice, they operated as bilateral exchanges where the principle of non-refoulement shifted from a legal protection to a point of political negotiation.

Externalization and Asymmetric Political Trade-offs

Trade-offs have also become increasingly apparent in the expanding reliance of contemporary return policies on readmission agreements and arrangements with origin and transit states. These frameworks typically combine incentives, such as aid, visas, or development cooperation with the threat of sanctions in cases of non-cooperation. Such deals often prioritize geopolitical and migration-management objectives over credible human rights

safeguards, particularly when partner states have weak protection systems, limited democratic oversight, or poor human rights records. As highlighted in recent debates on reforms to EU return regulations (2024-2025), the outsourcing of asylum processing and the establishment of return “hubs” in third countries can externalize legal and political responsibility, creating new trade-offs between domestic political gains and the capacity to uphold non-refoulement, accountability, and effective monitoring (DRC, 2024).

"Voluntariness" as Coercive Practice

Within assisted voluntary return (AVR) frameworks, human rights trade-offs can be understood as the consequences of policy measures that systematically exchange migrant rights, dignity, and agency for state migration control objectives and migrant financial incentives. These are not neutral exchanges; they redistribute harms and protections unevenly, with visible and invisible costs borne by returnees and invisible benefits accruing to origin and destination states.

AVR schemes are often presented as humane and rights-compliant alternatives to forced removal because they involve consent and provide some support. Yet the voluntariness they claim is often compromised by detention threats, legal limbo, and deprivation of basic rights such as work, housing, healthcare, and documentation—pressures designed to “encourage” departure. In reality, migrants face a coercive choice between accepting AVR with minimal aid or being forcibly deported. This system trades core human rights—due process, dignity, and non-refoulement—for policy efficiency and cost reduction, normalizing coercion as a migration management tool.

Procedural Trade-Offs and Identity Verification

Effective return procedures require accurate decisions, fair appeals, and reliable identity verification. However, states often streamline these processes to accelerate removals or meet return targets, undermining due process guarantees such as access to legal aid, individualized vulnerability and health assessments, and effective remedies—particularly within fast-track border or detention-based procedures. The trade-off here is between procedural robustness that reduces wrongful or harmful returns and managerial imperatives (costs, time, and political signalling) that favour rapid, low-safeguard processing (PICUM, 2022).

Even where formal standards exist that demand dignified treatment throughout the return process, monitoring shows recurring violations during apprehension, transfer, and removal, including excessive force or lack of medical care (OHCHR, 2024). These procedural shortcuts are particularly significant in bilateral frameworks like the Iraq-Germany arrangement, where identity verification through biometric data exchange and consular interviews becomes the mechanism by which “deportability” is established, sometimes with insufficient safeguards for those with contested or multiple national claims.

Post-Return Abandonment and Fragmented Reintegration

Human rights commitments extend beyond the physical act of removal to post-return conditions, including access to livelihoods, housing, health, and education. Many return and reintegration policies, however, invest minimally in long-term support or structurally ignore local political economies, leaving returnees marginalized, stigmatized, and at risk of re-migration or renewed displacement. The trade-off is between short-term performance metrics (e.g., numbers of returns, quick case closure) and investments in durable, rights-based reintegration that would require development, social policy, and protection resources in countries of origin (Kuschminder & Saguin, 2025). This gap is particularly acute in Iraq, where reintegration support is ad hoc, limited in duration, and difficult to access. Returnees frequently report receiving no training, employment assistance, or psychosocial support

despite formal promises in bilateral agreements; those who do receive financial assistance find amounts insufficient relative to migration costs and post-return livelihood needs, leaving them in survival mode rather than enabling genuine reintegration.

To conclude this section, framing these dynamics as “trade-offs” usefully exposes tensions between policy goals but risks normalizing the notion that certain rights are negotiable in the name of migration control. From a human rights standpoint, obligations such as non-refoulement and the prohibition of torture are absolute and cannot be balanced against enforcement or deterrence aims. Rhetoric around “voluntary, safe, and dignified” return conceals serious gaps in protection, consultation, and post-return support, as well as opaque exchanges that undermine the very humanitarian principles invoked by AVR programmes.

2. AVRs in Iraq

The historical context matters. When Iraq's Prime Minister visited Sweden in 2008, Iraqi officials framed return as a sign of restored security and state capacity, facilitating the 2008 Memorandum of Understanding (MOU) on voluntary return. Similarly, in 2023, Germany and Iraq formalized a "Declaration of Intent" emphasizing legal and labor migration cooperation—with voluntary return as a political quid pro quo in which Iraq accepts deportations in exchange for visa facilitation and development assistance. These agreements assert mutual benefits: host countries reduce irregular migration; Iraq receives development funding and demonstrates state control; migrants receive financial support and return assistance. Yet this framing obscures a fundamental asymmetry: states gain diplomatic capital, budget relief, and symbolic victories; individual migrants, by contrast, face constrained choices in environments stripped of legal protection and social services.

Voluntariness, as understood in human rights and refugee law, requires genuine alternatives and the capacity to choose without undue pressure. This report argues that “voluntariness” in AVR is constructed through coercion rather than genuine consent. Migrants enduring prolonged legal limbo, restricted work and housing access, detention threats, and minimal services face two functionally coercive options: accept AVR with limited support or face forced deportation. Neither reflects authentic voluntariness. The system effectively trades human rights—due process, non-refoulement, dignity, and socio-economic security—for policy cost-efficiency through bilateral exchanges that are rarely transparent, inadequately monitored, and produce outcomes that contradict AVR's humanitarian rhetoric.

As we demonstrate in this report, migrants whose asylum applications are rejected or who cannot obtain residence permits face an escalating regime of deprivation. In our case studies (returns of Iraqi migrants from Germany and Sweden) we observed and documented the following:

The legal distinction between voluntary and forced return is presented as meaningful to migrants: voluntary return carries financial incentives (€1,000-€2,000 upfront plus travel costs, vocational training vouchers); forced deportation carries no such assistance, plus stigma, potential trauma, and family separation. Yet the choice between them is structured by immigration authorities, not offered in conditions of freedom. As one returnee explained: “*We were faced with a false voluntary return, which was in fact a forced return.*”

In this context, the survey conducted by the HHRO with 153 individuals who returned from Germany and Sweden, referred to above, shows that 104 of them stated that the lack of residency was the reason for their return.

The survey also shows that 89 individuals who returned from Germany and Sweden received assistance to finance their return, either from the host country or from international organizations. Only five of the 153 individuals received vocational training or psychological

and social support. In contrast, none of these individuals received support to access a specific job.

	Number of Returnees
Germany	122
Sweden	31
Total:	153

	Reason for Returning was Not Obtaining Residency
Agree	28
Strongly Agree	76
Total:	104

	How did you Finance your Return?
Host country support	47
UNHCR	7
IOM	35
Total:	89

Number of Returnees who Received Training	5
Number of People who Received Support to Get a Job	0

3. Case Studies

3.1. The Iraqi-Swedish Readmission Agreement

On 18 February 2008, Sweden and Iraq signed a Memorandum of Understanding (MOU) on voluntary return, formally establishing a bilateral readmission framework that permitted Sweden to enforce returns of Iraqis whose asylum applications had been rejected. The agreement emerged in response to a dramatic policy shift: having granted protection to more Iraqis than all other EU Member States combined in 2006—with recognition rates reaching 91 percent—Sweden experienced an unprecedented surge in asylum applications, rising from 2,330 in 2005 to approximately 8,951 in 2006 and over 12,000 in 2008. The political pressure on Swedish municipalities, particularly Södertälje, where overcrowding and resource shortages reached crisis levels, combined with Swedish officials' concern over maintaining international credibility regarding migration management, created the conditions for negotiating return arrangements. The 2008 MOU signalled a dramatic tightening of Swedish asylum policy and was facilitated by Iraqi Prime Minister Nouri al-Maliki's May 2008 visit to Stockholm, during which Iraqi officials assured Swedish counterparts that security conditions had stabilized sufficiently to receive returning citizens (Al-Mohsen F., 2012).

The MOU stipulates that return occurs primarily on a voluntary basis, contingent on migrants' "freely expressed will" and informed knowledge of conditions in their target areas. However, Article 4 explicitly reserves Sweden's right to enforce deportation as a "last resort" for those refusing voluntary departure. Critically, the agreement frames Iraq's acceptance of returnees as conditioned on Swedish provision of development assistance and aid to Iraq, establishing a direct quid pro quo: Iraq receives international financial support and diplomatic recognition of its restored security, while Sweden gains a legal mechanism to reduce its asylum caseload and demonstrate restrictive migration management to domestic constituencies. The trade-off is institutional and political rather than humanitarian: Iraq's cooperation facilitates European migration control, while Iraqi state capacity for reception becomes secondary to bilateral convenience (Shakiry Charity, 2008).

Paradoxically, while the Iraqi Government did not formally deny these agreements, high-ranking officials simultaneously acknowledged their failures. Muhammad Salih Al-Hamdani, former Director General of the Legal Department at the Iraqi Ministry of Migration and Displacement (MOMD), documented systematic violations during the deportation process itself. He recorded 519 deportation cases from Sweden in 2009 alone, accompanied by reports of physical violence, handcuffing, drugging, and rapid forced removals (Buratha News, 2009). Al-Hamdani asserted that these practices violated both international law and the explicit terms of the 2008 MOU, which stipulates in Article 4 that “the two parties hereby acknowledge that the return of Iraqis should take place based on their freely expressed will in the first instance, and based on their knowledge of the prevailing situation in the places to which they wish to return.” The documented deportation practices—arrest without hearing, detention without individual assessment of circumstances, violent removal—fundamentally contradicted this commitment, constituting violations of Articles 3 and 5 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights protecting freedom from torture, degrading treatment, and arbitrary detention (Buratha News, 2009).

Returnees through the Swedish Migration Agency programme receive financial support structured in two tiers: approximately 30,000 Swedish Krona (USD 3,107) per adult and 15,000 SEK (USD 1,553) per child, with a family maximum of 75,000 SEK (USD 7,768) (MOFA, 2022). Applications must be submitted simultaneously with asylum rejection decisions, coordinated between the Swedish Migration Agency and the International Organization for Migration (IOM). Non-financial assistance is ostensibly more comprehensive, including airport reception, temporary accommodation, business establishment grants, labour market entry support, vocational training, career counselling, legal advice, and medical care. These supports are theoretically implemented through two primary actors: the European Technology and Training Centre (ETTC), which provides initial reintegration guidance in Iraq (particularly in Erbil and Sulaymaniyah), and IOM, which administers financial reintegration contributions and pre-departure counselling.

Evidence from field research and official sources reveals significant divergence between formal commitments and actual implementation. Following the 2008 agreement, over 800 Iraqis were forcibly deported from Sweden within several years, with many subjected to harsh treatment documented by Iraqi officials and human rights monitors. The terms “voluntary” and “forced” return categories often blurred in practice, as individuals facing detention, subsistence withdrawal, and restricted work access “opted” for AVR to avoid involuntary deportation. While AVRR programmes theoretically expanded to serve broader returnee populations, actual coverage remained limited: the programmes serve only a fraction of annual deportations, and returnee testimonies collected through the HHRO study (covering 31 returns from Sweden, of which 12 were forced) reveal that the majority received no vocational training, employment assistance, or psychosocial support despite formal programme descriptions promising these services. Financial assistance, when received, proved inadequate relative to returnees' migration costs (typically USD 10,000 or more) and reintegration needs, leaving recipients unable to establish sustainable livelihoods. Post-return contact with ETTC and IOM often ceased within weeks, leaving returnees isolated and dependent on informal family networks or facing re-migration as their only viable option.

The Gap Between Promise and Practice: Returnee Experiences from Sweden to Iraq

The HHRO team conducted interviews and a survey within the framework of GAPs project in 2024 among the returnees from Sweden which documented patterns of vulnerability and inadequate support. The experiences of returnees interviewed by the HHRO reveal a stark disjuncture between the formal provisions of the Sweden-Iraq MOU and the lived reality of those returned under its framework. Financial assistance, when received, rarely matches the costs of re-establishing livelihoods, while promised non-financial supports—vocational

training, employment assistance, psychosocial rehabilitation—are largely absent from returnees’ post-arrival experiences. The systematic withdrawal of such supports, combined with the structural coercion that frames AVR as preferable to forced deportation, transforms the voluntary return programme into a mechanism that trades dignity and agency for minimal fiscal transfers.

The case of returnee 20WGH–20MKA² illustrates this disparity acutely. A Baghdad resident, who returned from Sweden in 2023 under the AVR programme he received \$2,700 under the Assisted Voluntary Return Program, significantly below the SEK 75,000 family maximum and insufficient relative to the investment required for sustainable reintegration. Despite the MOU’s promises of labour market entry support, business establishment funds, and career counselling, he has found himself unable to access these programmes or engage with the National Referral Mechanism (NRM), leaving him isolated and unable to rebuild employment or social networks.

Returnee AHH9–WA9 presents a contrasting but equally precarious situation. Forcibly deported from Sweden in 2021 after nearly four years of legal residence during which he worked continuously, paid taxes, and fulfilled all civic obligations, he was denied access to the AVR programme entirely, receiving only IOM-funded transport. Forcibly deported from Sweden in 2021 after nearly four years of legal residence during which he worked continuously, paid taxes, and fulfilled all civic obligations to the host country. He was unable to obtain permanent residency, however, and did not receive any assistance under the AVRR, receiving only IOM funded transport. Upon arrival in Iraq, he received no non-cash assistance, such as training, employment, or psychological support. His testimony encapsulates the psychological consequence of this abandonment: Although he doesn’t regret his return, he feels pessimistic about the future, his resilience has weakened, and his health has deteriorated. He feels depressed and lonely all the time, believing that he cannot move on. This pattern—initial acceptance of return, followed by deepening depression and hopelessness as reintegration support fails to materialize—recurs across multiple testimonies and suggests that the trauma of return is compounded by post-arrival abandonment.

Ms. 19SYF–19PW, forcibly returned from Sweden in 2012 after living there for four years, explicitly frame herself as “a victim of political agreements” between Sweden and Iraq. Although she and her husband received \$11,000 from the Swedish Government, neither received training or psychosocial support. Nearly a decade after return, she remains unable to process her displacement: “*I feel afraid all the time and I rarely feel optimistic about the future.*” Her case exemplifies how financial compensation without complementary support services fails to address the psychological and social dimensions of forced return, leaving returnees trapped in cycles of fear and regret.

Returnee 29SYSH–29PW, an Iraqi Christian deported from Sweden in 2007 only after living there for two years and a ten-day detention period, received \$3,000 in assistance from the IOM, and was forced to finance his return journey by borrowing from family and friends, effectively transferring the cost of Sweden’s deportation policy onto his kinship networks. Like others, he received no training, employment, or psychological or social support. Notably, despite expressing intentions to re-migrate and regret over his return he maintains some optimism the future.

The case of returnee 27APG–27PW, a 43 years old Iraqi Christian forcibly returned in 2018 after three years as an asylum seeker in Sweden with no case resolution, reveals how prolonged legal limbo compounds post-return trauma. Living in rented accommodation in Baghdad with no family support—all siblings and relatives having emigrated—he has received no

² In accordance with the specific principles of this survey, the identity of volunteers remains anonymous and codes are used to identify each participant’s form.

reintegration support whatsoever. His testimony reflects profound social isolation and hopelessness: he intends to emigrate again if opportunity arises and has abandoned hope for his future in Iraq. The absence of family networks, combined with zero state or programme support, leaves him in a state of perpetual precarity, a living in a survival mode.

Returnee 14GAA–14MTO, 41 years old, who returned from Sweden in 2019 and received approximately USD 6000 through a non-governmental organization, summarizes the broader systemic failure. He believes that he has been experiencing a very difficult situation in Iraq since his return and that, according to him, there are no development programs. This assessment, repeated across multiple interviews, reveals that the promised infrastructure of reintegration support exists primarily on paper, not on the ground.

Returnee 33MQSH–33PW, a Christian from Ankawa in Erbil, was "arrested like any other terrorist criminal" and detained for a week specifically for deportation purposes, despite having filed an asylum application on grounds of religious persecution. His account captures the arbitrary nature of asylum determination: *"My asylum application was rejected, while applications were accepted at the same time as mine for people who had engaged in terrorist acts and crimes"*. Upon return to the Kurdistan Region of Iraq, he confronted not only social exclusion but also economic collapse—delayed salary payments for public employees and widespread administrative corruption—rendering formal employment inaccessible and deepening his frustration and immobility.

Returnee 31SHSM–31PW, an Iraqi Christian woman returned from Sweden in August 2016 with her disabled husband after only 18 months, exemplifies how disability and vulnerability status are rendered invisible in return procedures. Swedish authorities provided minimal assistance (3,600 SEK; approximately USD 371) and funded only transport, refusing to consider her husband's disability status or the couple's complete loss of assets, employment, and social support systems in Iraq. Her post-return state reflects cumulative trauma and abandonment: *"I feel scared, lonely and frustrated all the time since returning"*.

The most-stark case emerges from returnee 14DKS–14MKA, forcibly returned from Sweden in 2024 after more than 9 years of residence. His experience reveals how return policies intersect with family separation and state violence. Swedish authorities removed his four children (ages 12–19) from his custody in 2016 through "police-assisted child removal", leading to family dissolution and divorce. When he protested through public demonstration, he was arrested and imprisoned for five months and one week, after which his temporary residence was revoked and he was forcibly deported to Iraq. His description of post-return life—*"all he does after returning is an attempt to survive"*—encapsulates how forced return transforms from a migration management tool into a form of abandonment where returnees are left to navigate impossible circumstances without state, community, or kinship support

These testimonies illustrate significant gaps between the stated intentions of the Sweden-Iraq AVR framework and its implementation outcomes. The framework presents itself as a humanitarian mechanism facilitating safe and dignified return, yet returnees experience a narrowing of choices: facing restrictions on work authorization, housing access, and basic services in Sweden, individuals are presented with limited alternatives to AVR participation. While framed as voluntary, these conditions render the exercise of choice constrained rather than free. Financial assistance, though provided in some cases, often falls short of meeting the actual costs associated with return and establishing sustainable livelihoods in Iraq. Post-arrival support, including promised reintegration services such as vocational training, employment assistance, and psychosocial care, frequently remains inaccessible or terminates prematurely, leaving returnees to navigate reintegration independently. Additionally, returnees with particular vulnerabilities—Christian minorities facing religious persecution, persons with disabilities, individuals with protracted or complex asylum histories, and family members separated through state child-removal procedures—do not consistently receive

tailored protections or support adapted to their circumstances. This suggests that while the AVR framework aims to address migration management, it may inadvertently perpetuate or fail to adequately address pre-existing vulnerabilities rather than providing differentiated, needs-based assistance.

3.2. The Germany-Iraq Return Framework

In May 2023, Germany and Iraq formalized a “Declaration of Intent” on migration cooperation, establishing a non-legally binding framework for strengthening mutual engagement in legal migration, consular cooperation, repatriation, and integration services.³

Operating under Article 105, paragraph 3, of the EU-Iraq Partnership and Cooperation Agreement (2012), the Declaration emphasizes that, “legal migration benefits both societies and strengthens relations between them”, positioning labour mobility and voluntary return as mutually beneficial. The political quid pro quo embedded in this agreement is explicit: Germany commits to expedited visa processing for business travellers or students through reduced waiting times at the German Embassy in Baghdad and the German Consulate General in Erbil, while Iraq agrees to readmit not only those who have committed crimes in Germany but, as one analysis notes, “substantially all of its citizens whose asylum cases are rejected or deemed to be irregular” (Pro Asyl, 2023). This expansive readmission commitment represents a significant escalation in Iraq’s return obligations compared to previous frameworks.

A central operational challenge addressed in the Declaration concerns identity verification and biometric data exchange. Since many asylum seekers lack formal documentation, Germany and Iraq established protocols for consular interviews and biometric matching to establish nationality and deportability, theoretically enabling the processing of cases that would otherwise remain unresolved. The agreement thus frames identification and repatriation as mutually urgent technical problems requiring bilateral coordination.

The agreement also included the economic reintegration of returnees as a key part of sustainable reintegration, and the need to provide returnees with employment opportunities and rehabilitation where possible. Both sides further agreed on their willingness to involve the private sector, as well as governmental and non-governmental bodies to assist returnees, enhancing their economic and employment opportunities (Amal Frankfurt, 2023).

Assisted Voluntary Return Assistance Package

The Declaration of Intent includes a comprehensive AVR assistance package theoretically covering multiple dimensions of the return and reintegration process. Financial support includes travel cost coverage from Germany to Iraq €200 per person (€100 for persons under 18 years of age); medical support of up to €2,000 for up to three months after arrival in Iraq; one-time support after arrival of €1,000 per person (€500 for persons under 18 years of age, up to a maximum of €4,000 per family); additional financial support for reintegration 6–8 months after arrival of €400 per person under 18 years of age (up to a maximum of €800 per family) (Agenzia Nova, 2023). Beyond financial transfers, the Joint Reintegration Services Program promises short-term airport reception and transportation assistance and long-term support (up to twelve months) including in-kind payments (up to €2,000 for the main applicant and €1,000 for each additional family member) for housing, medical needs for serious illnesses, education and vocational training measures, job counselling and job search assistance, support in setting up a business, family reunification, legal advice and administrative support, as well as psychosocial support (Agenzia Nova, 2023).

³ Interview with 3MOHM (IOM Iraq).

On paper, this framework represents one of the most detailed and comprehensive return assistance architectures in the EU-Iraq bilateral context. However, field implementation reveals profound gaps between stated commitments and actual service delivery.

The scale of German deportations to Iraq has accelerated dramatically following the Declaration of Intent. In October 2023, approximately 26,000 Iraqis were issued deportation orders by the German Federal Interior Ministry (IntelliNews, 2024). By 2024, this translated into sustained operational deportations: the German Interior Ministry recorded 816 Iraqi deportations in 2024, including 615 direct returns to Iraq and others transferred under secondary asylum agreements with other European states. In July 2025, a departure from Leipzig Airport illustrated the operational scale and security apparatus surrounding these removals: deportees were transported from detention and accommodation centres via supervised minibuses and airport buses, with German police units overseeing boarding amid tight airport perimeter surveillance, apparently designed to minimize public visibility and protest. These operations have faced criticism from human rights organizations, particularly given the lack of guarantees for a safe environment for deportees in Iraq, which continues to suffer from fragile security and recurring internal unrest. These organizations emphasize that mass deportations may expose deportees to the risk of marginalization or even political retaliation, especially in tense areas such as the so-called “disputed territories,” where the majority of the population is made up of minorities. Returnees from abroad often face significant challenges in meeting their basic needs, such as food, shelter, and healthcare, leading some to consider leaving the country again (InfoMigrants, 2024).

Many Iraqis in Germany exist in prolonged legal limbo through *Duldung* (tolerance) residence permits—a status conferring restricted social assistance and limited work authorization while maintaining constant deportability. This liminal status, which can persist for years or even decades, creates perpetual insecurity and serves as structural pressure toward “voluntary” return participation.

Despite the formal comprehensiveness of the AVR package, returnee testimonies collected through the HHRO document systematic failures in implementation and accessibility. Most critically, the vast majority of interviewed returnees were unaware of the National Referral Mechanism (NRM) established by Iraq to coordinate reintegration services, and reported receiving limited practical assistance despite formal programme descriptions promising training, employment support, and psychosocial care.

In an interview with Ms. 1SRK–1WW, a woman from the Nineveh Plain who was forcibly deported from Germany and has a negative perception of return programs, she received €200 from the EU and was forcibly returned to Iraq without receiving any training or employment procedures in Iraq. She also did not receive any psychological or social support, and her family and friends were helping her integrate. She is unhappy about her return and intends to migrate again, saying that her next destination will likely be Australia. She described her return process, saying:

“I went to the immigration office in Stuttgart, Germany, for a regular visit, which is a regular visit every four months, and I was surprised to find that they had already booked me a plane ticket, and only gave my son, who was accompanying me, the flight number on which I was returning to Baghdad, without any other details.”

She added, *“They gave me €200 and I was taken from the immigration office in Stuttgart directly to the airport without even taking my personal belongings.”* She noted that the Iraqi authorities were not notified about her deportation. She landed at Baghdad Airport on 23 July 2024, and was not investigated. She did not see any members of the reception committee that is supposed to receive returnees, neither from the Migration and Displacement Ministry nor from the Higher Coordination Committee for Migration. She added, *“I returned to my home*

in the Nineveh Plain without being included in the NRM established by the Iraqi Government to govern return migration.”

This pattern repeats across multiple cases. Returnee 7NMYK–7WW, a Yazidi woman who returned voluntarily in 2021 with the legitimization that “lack of integration into German society” and the improved security situation in her area of origin, says that she did not receive any assistance, training, employment, or psychological support. Returnee 20HIA–20WW, despite holding a residency permit in Germany, was forcibly deported, detained four to five hours upon arrival for “routine investigation”, received €1,000 from the IOM, and subsequently received no training or psychological support, instead living in chronic loneliness, lonely and depressed, unable to move on, and fears for his future.

Returnee 21HKH–21WW, a returnee from Germany with a family of nine, revealed that he returned due to not having a permanent residence permit and cultural differences. He received \$700 from the IOM and did not receive any training, employment, or psychological or social support. He did not find any job opportunities and regrets his return to Iraq. He said that he intends on emigrating again and cannot move on with life in Iraq. Returnee MNJ8–WA8, forcibly returned in March 2024 after four years in Germany, received no assistance from the AVR programme and no non-monetary support, reporting: *“I deeply regret my return and intend to emigrate again. While I am able to adapt to changes, I feel depressed all the time.”* Returnee BAH3–WA3, deported after only eight months in Germany, received only USD 200 from IOM, faces unemployment and housing precarity, and describes perpetual depression, fear, and isolation. A key stakeholder observation from ETTC (European Technology and Training Centre) captures the systemic contradiction: *“Right, there is an agreement between Iraq and Germany, but there are obstacles in implementation and the next stages where others will be returned, but the issue is linked to the political situation. Also, many types of voluntary return occur compulsorily as a result of lack of services in the host country.”*

Particular vulnerability categories, such as minorities, receive inadequate differentiated support. Returnee 3WAM–3WW who returned from Germany in 2017 with an institute degree from the Nineveh Plain, a disputed area, and returned as part of the Safe Return Program, but none of his family remained in Iraq. He did not receive any financial assistance as part of the voluntary return assistance program, and relies on his savings, having not received any non-cash assistance, such as training, employment, or psychosocial support, since returning. He currently has no friends in Iraq and is depressed, wanting to emigrate again. Returnee, 93MNAB–93PW, an unskilled worker forcibly returned from Germany in 2024, says that he wants to emigrate again, but legally. He confirms that he has not received training, employment, or psychological support, suffers from depression, and has no friends.

The results of a 2023 survey conducted by the IOM also showed that nearly half of Iraqi returnees from Europe seriously considered attempting to migrate again within six months of their return. This reflects the failure of return policies to achieve stability or provide long-term solutions in light of the local reality in Iraq, which lacks security and decent living opportunities (Jusoor Post, 2025).

4. The Trade-offs in the Context of Return Migration in Iraq

One example of a bargaining chip included in migrant return agreements is the establishment of development programs in countries of origin. This constitutes a distinct form of political trade-off wherein development assistance becomes a mechanism through which host states fulfill commitments to Iraq while individual returnees remain excluded from direct benefit. The UNDP Funding Facility for Stabilization (FFS) completed stabilization projects in April 2023, in five liberated governorates (Anbar, Diyala, Kirkuk, Nineveh, and Salah al-Din) through 3,500 initiatives, including the rehabilitation of schools, hospitals, water stations,

electricity networks, and homes, as well as the provision of short-term employment opportunities. Sweden, through the Swedish International Development Cooperation Agency (SIDA), and the UN Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) in Iraq, sought to strengthen the resilience of farming households vulnerable to the impacts of climate change in the governorates of Maysan, Muthanna, Najaf, and Dhi Qar.

Germany has provided substantial grants to Iraq as part of the so-called “German Project” for economic enterprise development (Iraqi News Agency, 2023). These investments target national reconstruction and poverty reduction broadly, not returnee-specific reintegration. When a returning individual does not receive personal assistance, even though their country receives financial support from the host country as part of an exchange for developing agriculture, industry, or other types of support, they feel they have gained nothing, despite their country receiving these benefits. This creates a critical asymmetry: Iraq receives substantial development funding—framed as compensation for accepting returns—while individual returnees experience no direct benefit from these macroeconomic interventions. A returnee receives €1,000 or USD 2,700 in personal assistance while their country receives millions in development support; the state gains diplomatic recognition and international funding, while the individual gains subsistence-level cash and no meaningful employment or psychosocial support. This distributes the benefits of the “trade-off” upward to state institutions and downward minimally to individuals, creating frustration precisely because returnees perceive themselves as having sacrificed their livelihoods abroad without receiving equivalent compensation.

As a result of the barter agreements, the EU and some of its Member States began establishing returnee centres as part of their commitment to supporting Iraq in assisting and reintegrating returnees. In this context, the EU contributed to the establishment of two specialized centres (ICMPD and ETTC) that provide vocational training, psychosocial support, and business start-up assistance to returnees. These centres are funded by Germany, Switzerland, and the EU through their affiliated organizations operating in Iraq, including the German Corporation for International Cooperation (GIZ). Between June 2023 and May 2024, the centres provided “counselling and support” to approximately 350 returnees from Germany, the EU, and the region. In 2023, the IOM sponsored the “voluntary return” of 1,577 Iraqis seeking to return to their country from more than 20 countries, including Germany and Turkey. That same year, the Kurdish Rwanga Foundation launched a reintegration program, funded by Denmark and Finland. It also works to raise awareness with the aim of reducing irregular migration. Under this program, 120 people acquired vocational skills that enabled them to develop a “business plan” and establish their own small businesses. Fifteen of them received grants of between €4,000 and €5,000 (Swissinfo, 2025). These projects are often in “construction, carpentry, mobile phone and electronics repair, retail, food services, or even beauty services for women”. These programmes, while valuable, operate at marginal scale relative to total returnee populations: the HHRO survey of 153 returnees found that only 5 received vocational training or psychosocial support, and zero received job placement assistance.

Experiences of returnees

Among the beneficiaries of financial assistance is Muhammad Ismail, 29, who bought a share in an auto repair shop. In 2016, he arrived in Germany hoping to “improve his living conditions and obtain European citizenship.” After five years and eight months, however, he “did not achieve” his goal and was not granted a work permit, despite receiving assistance amounting to approximately €320 per month. These factors prompted him to agree to return to Iraq in April 2021, for which he received a total of €500 from Berlin and a UN agency. Today, he earns approximately \$550 per month and supports his wife and their three-year-old child. He is not thinking about emigrating again (DW, 2025).

Most critically, returnees remain systematically unaware of these services. The NRM, Iraq's National Referral Mechanism for coordinating reintegration, remains inaccessible to the vast

majority; returnees report never encountering reception committees, never receiving information about available programmes, and never being connected to ETTC or ICMPD services. This represents a profound implementation gap: the infrastructure exists, but the mechanisms for connecting returnees to it do not. Returnees instead rely on informal family networks and daily wage labour, while formal support systems remain institutional abstractions.

4.1. Alternative Solutions to Trade-offs in the Context of Return

4.1.1. Compensating Human Rights with Equal Assistance for Voluntary Return

A central human rights trade-off emerges from the radical mismatch between migration costs and return assistance. Illegal migration poses an economic and developmental threat to countries of origin, as it drains working-age youth, particularly qualified ones, in addition to its economic impact resulting from the large sums paid to migrant-smuggling networks that drain families' savings. Each illegal migration case costs approximately \$10,000, distributed between preparing a fake study or work file, or without that, as well as the payment to smugglers and other expenses, in addition to the continued coercion of migrants and their families to pay until the last moment of the smuggling operation (H. Al-Nasiri, 2023). Returnees receive EUR 1,000–2,700 in personal assistance, representing 10–27% cost recovery. This inadequacy creates a perverse incentive structure: the financial "loss" of return—abandoning investment already sunk into migration—remains so substantial that returnees view even modest reintegration support as insufficient compensation.

The HHRO survey reveals that 104 of 153 returnees cited lack of residency as their deportation reason, 89 received financial assistance from host countries or international organizations, yet only 5 received training and zero received job placement. The gap between promised support (vocational training, employment assistance, business grants) and actual delivery (cash transfers only) constitutes a systemic trade-off: financial transfers substitute for the labour-market access, skill-building, and employment that would enable genuine reintegration. Financial compensation without employment pathways produces survival, not integration.

We have previously explained the contributions provided by some European countries to safe return programs, but there is no clear budget for Iraqi institutions regarding the costs of migrants' safe return, as these overlap with the relevant government institutions' budgets, in addition to covering a large part of them through grants and projects implemented by international organizations and foreign development institutions. For example, on 3 March 2021, Migration and Displacement Minister Evan Faeq Jabro asked the German ambassador to assist Iraqis wishing to voluntarily return to their country and to increase the grants and aid amounts provided to them, "in a way that guarantees them a decent life, stability and the provision of financial resources upon their return" (DW, 2021).

Another key human rights trade-off emerges from the construction of "voluntary" return through deprivation. Migrants in Germany holding *Duldung* permits experience institutionalized precarity: restricted work authorization, minimal social assistance, and perpetual deportability maintained for years or decades. The same is valid for Sweden. Migrants who received a return order literally "cut off" from the system. This legal limbo creates structural pressure toward AVR participation: accepting €1,000 and deportation appears preferable to indefinite suspension between work prohibition and removal threat. The choice is functionally coercive. The GAPS survey results (conducted by HHRO) underscore this: 29 of 153 returnees report considering illegal re-migration despite formal return through bilateral agreements; 83 describe their post-return existence as "just trying to survive"; 25 report persistent depression; 20 state they "cannot move on". Only 52 of 153 report satisfaction with return; 78 express unhappiness. These outcomes suggest that "voluntary" return

functions not as genuine choice but as constrained acceptance of the least harmful available option under conditions of systematic deprivation.

As our interview accounts show, the assistance received by returnees as part of the voluntary return assistance program did not match the amount of money spent by migrants. This was in addition to the suffering they endured during migration, having been subjected to poor trafficking and harsh treatment by migration brokers, as well as the constant danger, fear, and anxiety they experienced throughout their experience. The decision to return, therefore, is not easy for migrants unless there are financial and non-financial incentives that encourage them to return safely, with dignity, and in an orderly manner. Furthermore, it is difficult for migrants to return unless they receive information about the level of return migration governance in their country of origin, in terms of stability and security, improved economic conditions, as well as access to the labour market, education, health, and other services. Migrants often receive misleading or unrealistic information that hinders the return process.

Human rights organizations in Iraq have warned of the repercussions of the increasing number of migrants seeking a homeland that guarantees their rights and meets their legitimate needs. These organizations hold successive governments responsible for the migration of skilled and energetic youth abroad due to their inability to provide the requirements for a decent life after 2003. Meanwhile, the majority of Iraqis who wish to emigrate are using various legal and illegal means to obtain asylum in European countries, escaping the unrest and insecurity that the country has witnessed over the past two decades. The GAPs/HHRO survey indicates that 19% of those who returned to Iraq from Sweden and Germany after failing to obtain permanent residency are considering emigrating again unless the country's stability and security improve, the economy develops, and access to work, education, and healthcare opportunities are met to an acceptable level (Al Rafidain TV, 2023).

A real-life example showing the costs of migration

After ten years of legal residency in Germany, MJ, middle-age, was deported to the Kurdistan Region of Iraq, where he is trying to rebuild his life from scratch amid abject poverty. Upon returning to his hometown of Ranya in Sulaymaniyah Governorate, he resided with his elderly father in a cramped apartment where they sleep on thin foam mattresses on a concrete floor. He is unemployed and finds it difficult to find work in Iraqi Kurdistan. He still wants to return to Europe if there is a way back and if his asylum application is accepted in Germany. His migration journey began in 2015, after he had saved a large sum of money to cover travel costs and smugglers. He travelled to Istanbul, then to Izmir, where he boarded a boat that clandestinely took him to a Greek island. From there, he travelled to Athens, then to North Macedonia, Serbia, Croatia, and finally Germany. There, he stayed in an asylum-seeker centre in the country's south and began receiving approximately €300 per month from the German State. He was sometimes forced to travel to Nuremberg, more than 150 kilometres to the north, and Munich, about 140 kilometres to the south, to work "illegally for two or three months during the winter," when searches for people working illegally were reduced. After his asylum application was rejected twice, German authorities deported him to Iraq in January 2024. He then tried to open a bakery, but failed. For two months, he worked selling falafel for a daily wage of about seven US Dollars. Today, he lives in Iraq on \$150 sent each month by relatives in the United Kingdom (DW, 2025).

The psychological impact of coerced return and subsequent abandonment is profound and quantifiable. The survey of 153 returnees from Germany and Sweden reveals:

- 78 expressed unhappiness with their return (51%)
- 29 stated they are considering emigrating again (19%)
- 83 report that everything they do is merely attempting to survive (54%)
- 25 report depression "all the time" (5-7 days weekly) (16%)
- 20 report inability to "move on" (13%)
- Only 28 expressed optimism and hope for the future (18%)

4.1.2. Political Instability and Abandoned Commitments

The human rights trade-off extends to state-level implementation failure. The Iraqi Parliament discussed the implementation of the MOU with Sweden in its 36th session on 10 October 2011, where MPs criticized the forced return procedures and the lack of respect for the international law principle of non-refoulement (Iraqi Parliament Archive, 2011). In its 39th parliamentary session on 5 May 2012, MPs spoke negatively about this issue, stating that the conditions in Iraq are not suitable for the deportation of asylum seekers to Iraq, and that the migrants had fled the terrorism that controlled many areas of the country until 2017. MPs demanded that a decision be issued to prevent the government from receiving refugees returning under this Memorandum (Iraqi Parliament Archive, 2011). The Iraqi Parliament also requested that the Iraqi MOFA amend the MOU to reflect the Parliament members' concerns. The MOFA, however, ignored these requests, and media statements by MPs and politicians continued to exploit this crisis and promote solutions that may be illegal and contradict Iraqi state policy, yet are consistent with migrants' desires to remain in their host countries (Hathalyoum, 2012). This institutional bypassing of parliamentary scrutiny and human rights concerns demonstrates that return agreements become insulated from domestic accountability through diplomatic convenience.

Political instability in Iraq—reflected in inter-bloc parliamentary disputes, inability to provide basic services, and security fragmentation—directly undermines returns and returnee reintegration. Economic collapse, delayed public sector salaries (particularly in Kurdistan Region), administrative corruption, and unemployment make formal employment inaccessible even for qualified returnees. The trade-off here is explicit: host countries externalize migration management costs to Iraq, which absorbs returnees into an environment of institutional failure and economic precarity, leaving returnees unable to rebuild livelihoods or achieve stability. This has also become evident in GAPS/HHRO research in Iraq: many returning migrants consider emigrating again. As stated above, the GAPS/HHRO survey, showed that 29 people out of a total of 153 were returned to Iraq from Germany and Sweden, and despite this taking place under bilateral agreements between Iraq on the one hand and Germany and Sweden on the other, they are thinking about illegal immigration again. Of them, 83 confirmed that everything they do is just an attempt to survive, while 28 expressed their optimism and hope for the future in Iraq, 25 indicated that they feel depressed all the time, and 20 confirmed that they constantly cannot move on. However, 52 people out of a total of 153 said that they are happy to be back in Iraq, while 78 of them expressed their unhappiness about the return and 23 of them were neutral.

4.1.3. Vulnerability and Differential Harm: Yazidis and Religious Minorities

Yazidi returnees exemplify how human rights trade-offs distribute harm unevenly across vulnerable categories. The decision to deport 5,000 Iraqi migrants from Germany 2023 has angered both Iraqi refugees and government agencies, particularly since most of these refugees belong to the Yazidi community, which was subjected to “genocide” during ISIS’ control of Nineveh Governorate in 2014. While the Iraqi MOMD affirms its rejection of any forced deportation of Iraqis abroad, it has also repeatedly stated that Iraq rejects the forced return of Iraqis from any country. The Ministry is in contact with relevant international bodies to assess the situation of Iraqis in Germany and other countries in this regard.

Given these conditions for the Yazidis, their return remains challenging due to the instability in their regions. Interviews by HHRO with Yazidis forcibly repatriated from Germany show they are living in harsh conditions, with some having no shelter and lacking the financial resources to rent one. As a result, they stay in squalid camps in Duhok, where healthcare, mental health, and social support are inadequate, and most find it difficult to access employment.

In this regard, returnee 6KHM–6PW, a Yazidi who fled Iraq in 2015 after escaping ISIS brutality, said that he was forcibly returned from Germany in September 2024, after living

there for 96 months. He is considering emigrating again because of the dire living conditions he faces. His family of 13 lives in a 4-square-meter tent in the forcibly displaced persons' camp at Cham-Mishko, near the northern Iraqi city of Zakho, close to the Iraqi–Turkish border. He is unemployed and unable to easily access work, as he works for daily wages. He also asserts, “*We were detained for a week in Germany before being deported.*” He is constantly afraid for the future.

Another returnee 50HMS–50PW, an Iraqi Yazidi, was forcibly deported from Germany in January 2025 after living there for 110 months. Police arrested and escorted him to the airport and a plane to Iraq via Dusseldorf. He returned to Iraq and is residing with his mother in the Sharia camp, near Duhok in the Kurdistan Region. German authorities deported him without regard for his social and humanitarian situation, keeping his children and wife in Germany while separating him from his family. He says, “*I am surprised at this action by a democratic country: to deport me to a place, a camp for displaced persons in Iraq, far from my family who remained in Germany. Here, I have no work or any assistance, and I live in a miserable situation with the other displaced people residing in the camp. I do not understand how Germany, a democratic country, would treat me this way and forcibly remove me from my wife and children.*” This represents a compounded trade-off: the individual trades security and legal residence in Germany for deportation that severs family ties and returns him to conditions of internal displacement.

Displaced Yazidis in Iraq continue to face increasing difficulties under the “Declaration of Intent” agreement concluded between the German and Iraqi governments to facilitate the return of migrants. Meanwhile, German authorities continue to receive thousands of Yazidi immigration applications annually. Migrant Shahab Samouqi, 21, says that he fears for his life if returned to Iraq after Germany rejected his asylum application. In Samouqi’s case, he has been living in Hamburg for several years, having fled his hometown of Sinjar due to the persecution of Yazidis at the hands of ISIS terrorist forces. Samouqi also asserts that he may be killed if circumstances force him to return to his homeland (Shafaq News, 2024).

During interviews conducted by the HHRO with Yazidis, information emerged about the impersonation of Yazidis by many migrants (especially Kurds due to the similarity of language and ethnicity). Dozens of migrants who registered as Yazidis in their applications for protection and residency took advantage of these circumstances. Some of them were discovered, however, which led to an impact on the stories of genuine Yazidi asylum seekers. This process undermines the confidence of host countries among Yazidi asylum seekers and affects their acceptance, as host-country immigration departments may impose restrictions and additional investigations, and demand evidence and supporting documents, proving the credibility of persons being subjected to religious or ethnic persecution, or a threat to life. This reverses the human rights framework: rather than protection being strengthened, it becomes contingent on proving persecution through bureaucratic filters that exclude those without formal documentation of trauma.

5. Discussion and Conclusion

Lack of Genuine Voluntariness: Was the so-called voluntary return truly voluntary and supported? Unfortunately, many of the cases that participated in the survey indicated that they (individuals or families) were in a situation that forced them to accept any offer of voluntary return to escape at the lowest possible cost, given the severe restrictions imposed on them by immigration authorities. In some cases, they were faced with two choices: forced return or acceptance of the voluntary return program. During the AVR process, they were subjected to coercive conditions and procedures that sometimes did not respect human dignity. As described by the majority of respondents to the survey, “*We were faced with a false voluntary*

return, which was in fact a forced return.” They even openly declared their desire to try to emigrate again when the opportunity arose.

The Inadequacy of Compensation Models: Across Sweden-Iraq and Germany-Iraq return frameworks, returnee testimonies reveal consistent patterns: financial assistance received without vocational training; promised employment support never materialized; psychosocial care absent despite documented trauma; accessibility to formal reintegration programmes minimal or non-existent. The GAPS/HHRO survey quantifies this: of 153 returnees, only 5 received training, zero received job placement, yet all experienced the transition from legal residence (even with restricted status) to precarious employment or unemployment in Iraq.

This consistent gap between bilateral agreement language and actual implementation highlights a core human rights trade-off. Return agreements are often negotiated and presented with humanitarian language- terms like “voluntary, ” “safe, ” “dignified, ” and “with support”- but their implementation relies on mechanisms that favour migration control efficiency over individual protection. This structural trade-off is inherent in AVRR models. From testimonies, we see that promises of reintegration support facilitate rapid deportations by giving an illusion of humanitarian management. In reality, support delivery is frequently underfunded, fragmented, and hard to access. Consequently, returnees face human costs, which are evident in outcomes such as unemployment, depression, family separation, and insecurity.

The political and human rights trade-off in the context of assisted voluntary return are driven by divergent interests. The first concerns the state's sovereignty, whose bilateral relations are affected by the acceptance of returning migrants in exchange for various benefits, given its insistence on respecting the non-refoulement principle and the human rights of returnees. The second concerns the individual interests of migrants who have exhausted all means of achieving permanent residency and are in a situation where they are implicitly forced to accept repatriation in exchange for financial benefits and future arrangements to guarantee the right to a decent living and development. When applying the general criteria for human-rights trade-off to the case of Iraq, two agreements that have generated considerable criticism as they led to the return of large groups of Iraqi migrants, particularly from Sweden and Germany, as well as from other EU countries that benefited from these agreements.

In light of the interviews conducted and the information obtained, we conclude the following political and human rights trade-offs in Iraq's return agreements:

1. The AVR frameworks did not emerge from equal negotiations between parties. Rather, both the Iraqi Government and Iraqi migrants faced compulsory acceptance: Iraq received development assistance and diplomatic recognition contingent on readmitting its citizens, while migrants confronted constrained choices between forced deportation and “voluntary” return with minimal support.
2. The bilateral agreements (Sweden-Iraq 2008 MOU; Germany-Iraq 2023 Declaration of Intent) were not subject to public consultation or civil society review during drafting and early implementation phases. This lack of transparency generated doubt and contestation upon implementation, as affected populations and advocacy organizations discovered commitments already operationalized without their input or consent.
3. The development programs and infrastructure mentioned in agreements, such as UNDP stabilization projects, SIDA agricultural support, and German economic grants, are not explicitly connected to benefits or outcomes for returnees. These are framed as state-level development assistance rather than returnee-specific reintegration, creating ambiguity about whether macroeconomic investments constitute fulfilment of humanitarian obligations to return populations.

4. These agreements lack independent monitoring mechanisms, complaint procedures, or external accountability structures. Implementation remains entirely within the discretion of immigration authorities in host countries and receiving institutions in Iraq, with no intermediate oversight by human rights bodies, civil society monitors, or judicial review mechanisms.
5. The bargain has fundamental human rights tradeoffs, which begin with the implementation of forced or assisted voluntary return (which cannot be confirmed as entirely voluntary). Implementation frequently includes documented human rights violations: arbitrary detention before departure, excessive force during apprehension, insufficient time for personal affairs preparation, family separation, and degrading treatment during transport and removal. The trade-off is explicit: migrants exchange foundational protections (due process, dignity, family integrity) for the option of returning with minimal financial support. The lack of mechanisms to challenge exchange procedures leaves victims with the *fait accompli* of accepting the new reality and remaining silent about the errors accompanying the voluntary repatriation process. Additionally, returnees report limited awareness of or access to these programmes, rendering them functionally unavailable despite formal inclusion in bilateral frameworks.

6. Recommendations

1. Future agreements, bilateral return agreements, and renegotiations of existing frameworks should undergo public consultation and parliamentary review before they are finalised. They should be formalized via constitutional or legislative processes, not by executive actions, to guarantee parliamentary oversight and legal accountability within the country. It is essential to systematically gather and integrate the perspectives of CSOs, including specialized returnee advocacy groups, human rights monitors, and associations representing deportees, into the process of agreement development.
2. Return agreements must clearly cite binding international human rights commitments—such as non-refoulement, the prohibition of torture, and due process—to avoid being viewed as simple diplomatic accords that are subordinate to migration control priorities.
3. Return agreements should involve independent oversight from national human rights institutions, international human rights organisations, or designated civil society monitors throughout all stages of return—pre-departure, removal, and post-arrival reintegration. Additionally, returnees must have access to appeal processes to ensure fairness and prevent arbitrary actions or deviations from the agreed objectives.
4. Development component of return agreements must explicitly link macroeconomic projects to returnee outcomes, establishing measurable targets for returnee employment generation, livelihood creation, and social reintegration.
5. Host and origin countries should explore mechanisms for fair cost-sharing related to return and reintegration. Returnees must be compensated justly and fairly on this basis, taking into account the full costs of migration (income foregone, interrupted education, and family separation). Compensation should support genuine economic reintegration through sustainable grants that significantly surpass current levels, along with employment, housing, and business start-up assistance.
6. Monetary and in-kind assistance provided to returnees must be sufficient to enable genuine livelihood establishment rather than temporary survival. Support should extend for minimum 12–24 months post-arrival, with renewal possible based on demonstrated need and integration progress. Comprehensive vocational training programmes must be expanded and made accessible to all returnees, considering the bureaucratic obstacles

restrictions in accessing these programmes. Facilitating returnees' access to work in the country of origin by providing interest-free loans without restrictive conditions, as well as providing housing benefits through various means that enable them to integrate and live with dignity.

In summary, all return frameworks should be based on the idea that return is a human right, exercised through real voluntary decision-making rather than a tool for migration control enforced by limited options or coercion. Protections for human rights—such as non-refoulement, due process, dignity, family integrity, and freedom of movement—are essential and should not be compromised for the sake of state migration goals. When conflicts between these rights and migration objectives occur, human rights must take precedence, even if this makes migration management or deportation more challenging.

7. References

- Ahmed I., 2015. *Youth migration threatens Iraq's future*. [Online] Available at: <https://www.albayan.ae> [Accessed: August 14, 2025].
- Agenzia Nova, 2023. *The secret agreement between Germany and Iraq on migrants*. [Online] Available at: <https://www.agenzianova.com> [Accessed: August 10, 2025]
- Al-Issawi M., 2015. *Increase in the number of migrants forces the government to undertake comprehensive reforms*. [Online] Available at: <https://kerbalacss.uokerbala.edu.iq> [Accessed: August 16, 2025].
- Al-Mohsen F., 2012. *Summary of the Swedish–Iraqi agreement on asylum seekers*. [Online] Available at: <https://alkompis.se> [Accessed: August 06, 2025].
- Al-Nasiri H., 2023. *From Baghdad via Russia to Europe: Iraqi youth are commodities for human trafficking networks*. [Online] Available at: <https://jummar.media> [Accessed: August 23, 2025].
- Al Rafidain TV, 2023. *A bleak future pushes Iraqis to migrate in search of lost dignity*. [Online] Available at: <https://alrafidain.tv> [Accessed: August 12, 2025].
- Amal Frankfurt, 2023. *Revealing a secret agreement between Germany and Iraq*. [Online] Available at: <https://amalfrankfurt.de> [Accessed: August 01, 2025].
- Bayan Center, 2016. *Thousands of Iraqi migrants return home, disappointed with Europe*. [Online] Available at: <https://www.bayancenter.org> [Accessed: August 10, 2025].
- Buratha News, 2009. *Collective deportations of Iraqi refugees in Sweden*. [Online] Available at: <https://burathanews.com> [Accessed: August 13, 2025].
- Collet & Sommerville, 2014. *Trade-Offs in Immigration Enforcement*. [Online] Available at: <https://www.migrationpolicy.org> [Accessed: December 13, 2025].
- DRC, 2024. *Surrendering Human Rights for Migration Control*. [Online] Available at: <https://drc.ngo> [Accessed: December 13, 2025].
- DW, 2021. *Baghdad calls on Berlin to assist Iraqis wishing to return voluntarily*. [Online] Available at: <https://www.dw.com> [Accessed: August 13, 2025].
- DW, 2025. *The bitterness of return: Migrants deported from Germany and Europe to Iraq*. [Online] Available at: <https://www.dw.com> [Accessed: August 10, 2025].
- Hathalyoum, 2012. *Parliament Presidency Calls on Foreign Ministry to Clarify Reasons for Its Rejection*. [Online] Available at: <https://hathalyoum.net> [Accessed: August 02, 2025].
- Huges K., 2025. *Ensuring Rights Protections in Cases of both Voluntary and Involuntary Return*. [Online] Available at: <https://perryworldhouse.upenn.edu> [Accessed: December 13, 2025].

- InfoMigrants, 2024. *Investigative report exposes secret deportation deal between Germany and Iraq*. [Online] Available at: <https://www.infomigrants.net> [Accessed: August 12, 2025].
- IntelliNews, 2024. *Germany steps up Iraqi Kurdish deportations under secret Baghdad deal*. [Online] Available at: <https://www.intellinews.com> [Accessed: December 31, 2025].
- Iraqi News Agency, 2023. *European Union: International support to revitalize small and medium-sized enterprises in Iraq*. [Online] Available at: <https://ina.iq> [Accessed: August 06, 2025].
- Iraqi Parliament Archive, 2011. *Minutes of Session No. 36, Monday 10-10-2011*. [Online] Available at: <https://archive12.parliament.iq> [Accessed: August 05, 2025].
- Jusoor Post, 2025. *Germany departs a new group of Iraqi migrants to Baghdad*. [Online] Available at: <https://jusoorpost.com> [Accessed: August 05, 2025].
- Kalach G., and Rimmer C., 2025. *Voluntary Return: An Overview of Policies and Practices*. [Online] Available at: <https://rm.coe.int> [Accessed: December 13, 2025].
- Kuschminder K., and K. Saguin. 2025. "Comparative Analysis of Reintegration Policies." *International Migration* 63, no. 4: e70072. [Online] Available at: <https://doi.org> [Accessed: December 13, 2025].
- Ministry of Foreign Affairs Iraq, 2022. *Voluntary Return - Rights of voluntary returnees to Iraq*. [Online] Available at: <https://mofa.gov.iq> [Accessed: August 05, 2025].
- OHCHR, 2024. *Human rights in the context of return*. [Online] Available at: <https://www.ohchr.org> [Accessed: December 13, 2025].
- PICUM, 2022. *Barriers to return: Protection in International, EU and National Frameworks*. [Online] Available at: <https://picum.org> [Accessed: December 13, 2025].
- Pro Asyl, 2023. *Declaration of intent*. [Online] Available at: <https://www.proasyl.de> [Accessed: August 07, 2025].
- Shafaq News, 2024. *Yazidis in Germany: Thousands of Asylum Requests and Fears of Deportation to Iraq*. [Online] Available at: <https://shafaq.com> [Accessed: August 01, 2025].
- Shakiry Charity, 2008. *Iraq and Sweden sign memorandum of understanding to organize voluntary return of Iraqi refugees*. [Online] Available at: <https://shakirycharity.org> [Accessed: August 06, 2025].
- Swissinfo, 2025. *Bitter return for migrants who left Europe for Iraq*. [Online] Available at: <https://www.swissinfo.ch> [Accessed: August 15, 2025].
- Valentine et al., 2024. *Mixed Returns: Return Migration and Reintegration Dynamics*. [Online] Available at: <https://mixedmigration.org> [Accessed: December 13, 2025].
- Warda, W. and Al-Bayati K, 2025. *Return Migration Infrastructures in Iraq – Country Dossier WP3, GAP's Project: De-centring the Study of Migrant Returns and Readmission Policies in Europe and Beyond*. [Online] Available at: <https://zenodo.org> [Accessed: July 25, 2025].